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New and rare Myxomycetes from the South-West of Crimea

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Investigations of Myxomycetes (Eumycetozoa) have been carried out in Crimean peninsula several times. The first detailed records were published by Yu.K. Novozhilov (1988) for the Cape Martyan Nature Reserve. Subsequent field collection lists were published for the Yalta Mountain-Forest Nature Reserve (Dudka et al., 1999; Dudka, 2000; Leontyev, 2005). Finally, detailed investigation of the myxomycete biota was provided for the Crimean Nature Reserve (Romanenko, 2006). Now the list of myxomycetes known for Crimea amounts to 137 species. Nevertheless, no data on myxomycete diversity from the abovementioned reserves have been published so far. The species composition in most of the territories of the peninsula is still unknown and further investigations are needed.

During the 6th International Congress on Systematics and Ecology of Myxomycetes in October 2008, we collected fructifications of myxomycetes (fc) and substrates for moist chamber cultures (mc) in three points of South-West Crimea: the Angara valley (44°45'N/34°20'E), the Baydar valley (44°24'N/33°46'E) and the Karalez valley (44°36'N/33°44'E). As a result of our research nine taxa (eight species and one variety) of myxomycetes were found new for Crimea (*); all of them, except one, appeared to be new for Ukraine (**). Another three species which are rare in the region, and probably for the country as a whole, being found in Crimea only once. A list of these species with ecological data is given below.

****Amaurochaete atra* (Alb. & Schwein.) Rostaf.** – wood and bark of *Pinus pallasiana* D. Don. (scorched trunk), Angara Valley, Elkh-Kaya, mountain *Fagus-Carpinus* forest, fc, 10.10.2008.

*****Clastoderma pachypus* Nann.-Bremek.** – bark of living *Quercus pubescens* Willd., Angara Valley, Pahkal-Kaya, mountain *Fagus-Carpinus* forest, mc, 10.10.2008.

***Comatricha tenerima* (M. A Curtis) G. Lister** – fallen twig of *Fagus orientalis* Lipsky, Angara Valley, Pahkal-Kaya, mountain *Fagus-Carpinus* forest, fc, 10.10.2008.

*****Dianema harveyi* Rex** – bark of living *Fraxinus* cf. *oxycarpa* M. Bieb. ex Willd., Angara Valley, Pahkal-Kaya, mountain *Fagus-Carpinus* forest, mc, 10.10.2008.

*****Dictydiaethalium ferrugineum* Nann.-Bremek.** – wood of *Carpinus orientalis* L., Karalez valley, Cave town Eski-Kermen, 'shiblyak' forest on plateau slopes, fc, 08.10.2008.

***Didymium sturgisii* Hagelst** – bark of living *Fraxinus* cf. *oxycarpa* M. Bieb. Ex Willd., Angara Valley, Elkh-Kaya, mountain *Fagus-Carpinus* forest, mc, 10.10.2008.

***Licea belmontiana* Nann.-Bremek.** – bark of living *Fagus orientalis* L., Angara valley, Elkh-Kaya, mountain *Fagus-Carpinus* forest; bark of living *Quercus pubescens* Willd. and *Acer* cf. *stevenii* Pojark., Angara Valley, Pahkal-Kaya, mountain *Fagus-Carpinus* forest; mc, 10.10.2008.

*****Licea scintillans* R. McHugh et D. W. Mitch.** – bark of living *Acer* cf. *stevenii* Pojark., Angara Valley, Pahkal-Kaya, mountain *Fagus-Carpinus* forest, mc, 10.10.2008.

*****Physarum pusillum* (Berk et M. A Curtis) G. Lister** – bark of living *Acer* cf. *stevenii* Pojark., Angara Valley, Pahkal-Kaya, mountain *Fagus-Carpinus* forest; mc, 10.10.2008

*****Stemonitopsis aequalis* (Peck) Y. Yamam.** – dead wood of deciduous tree and fallen twigs, Angara Valley, mountain *Fagus-Carpinus* forest, fc, 05.07.2005. Coll. et det. K.A. Fefelov.

*****Trichia contorta* (Ditmar) Rostaf. var. *iowensis* (T. Macbr.) Torrend** – wood of *Carpinus orientalis* L., Angara Valley, Elkh-Kaya, mountain *Fagus-Carpinus* forest, mc, 10.10.2008.

*****Trichia mirabilis* Nann.-Bremek.** – wood of *Carpinus orientalis* L., Angara Valley, Elkh-Kaya, mountain *Fagus-Carpinus* forest, mc, 10.10.2008.